

DESIGN AND STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF THE RIBS AND SPARS OF SWEEPED BACK WING

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Abstract:

The aim of this paper is to design and analyze the ribs and spars of a 150 seater regional aircraft for the stresses and displacements due to the applied loads. For this we did a comparative study on particular 150 seater regional aircraft. The optimum design parameters are suitably selected and then the model was designed using the CATIA software. The airfoil coordinates for the model to be designed, were generated by design foil software. The major wing design parameters were explained in detail and the wing configuration has been described. Different types of loads acting on the aircraft and the wing are determined and the moments, displacements, etc., are also determined. The wing structure was also explained and functions of each component and their arrangement are also studied. The methodology of finite element method and the detailed description about various FEM tools have been studied and implemented in this work.

Introduction:

Aim:

To find the capability of aircraft wing structure to withstand bending moment and to pressure loading.

Definition of Wing:

The wing is a framework made up of spars and ribs and covered with metal. Wing structures carry some of the heavier loads found in the aircraft structure. The particular design of a wing depends on many factors, such as the size, weight, speed, rate of climb, and use of the aircraft. Wing is mainly used as a lift producing component in an aircraft.

Wing Support:

Based on the support provided in the wing to the fuselage, the wing can be classified into the following types

Cantilevered:

All the structure is buried under the aerodynamic skin, giving a clean appearance with low drag.

Braced:

The wings are supported by external structural members

- Strut Braced
- Wire Braced

Aspect Ratio:

The aspect ratio is the span divided by the mean or average chord. It is a measure of how long and slender the wing appears when seen from above or below.

Wing Sweep:

Swept back from the root, the wing angles backwards towards the tip. At transonic speeds swept wings have lower drag, but can handle badly in or near a stall and require high stiffness to avoid aero-elasticity at high speeds.

Figure 1: Swept Back Wing

Components of Wing:

The internal wing structure, consisting of spars, ribs and stringers, and the external wing, which is the skin.

Figure 2: Components of Wings

Spars:

Spars are the main structural members of the wing, running spanwise at right angles to the fuselage. The spar carries flight loads and the weight of the wings whilst on the ground. Other structural and forming members such as ribs may be attached to the spar or spars, with stressed skin construction also sharing the loads where it is used.

Some of the forces acting on a wing spar are

- Upward bending loads resulting from the wing lift force that supports the fuselage in flight. These forces are often offset by carrying fuel in the wings or employing wing-tip –mounted fuel tanks.
- Downward bending loads whilst stationary on the ground due to the weight of the structure, fuel carried in the wings, and wing-mounted engines if used.
- Drag loads dependent on airspeed and inertia.
- Rolling inertia loads.
- Chord wise twisting loads due to aerodynamic effects at high airspeeds often associated with washout, and the use of ailerons resulting in control reversal

Advantages of the Spars:

- The spars are the most heavily loaded parts of an aircraft. They carry much more force at its root, than at the tip.
- Spars are used to carry Shear forces and Bending Moments of the wing.

Ribs:

Ribs give the shape to the wing section, support the skin (prevent buckling) and act to prevent the fuel surging around as the aircraft maneuvers. They serve as attachment points for the control surfaces, flaps, under carriage and engines. The ribs need to support the wing-panels, achieve the desired aerodynamic shape and keep it, provide points for conducting large forces, add strength, prevent buckling, and separate the individual fuel tanks within the wing. Milled ribs are solid structures, manufactured by milling away excess material from the solid block of metal, and are also used where very high loads apply.

Load Acts on Ribs:

They transmit the air load from the wing covering to the spars, Ribs extend from the leading edge to the trailing edge of the wing.

Advantages of Ribs:

- Ribs give the shape to the wing section.
- They serve as attachment points for the control surfaces, flaps, undercarriage and engines.
- The ribs need to support the wing-panels and to achieve the desired aerodynamic shape.
- It is used to provide Strength and prevent Buckling.

Aerofoil Selection:

Symmetrical Airfoils:

Symmetrical airfoils have identical upper and lower surfaces. They are suited to rotary-wing applications because they have almost no center of pressure travel. Travel remains relatively constant under varying angles of attack, affording the best lift drag ratios for the full range of velocities from rotor blade root to tip. However, the symmetrical airfoil produces less lift than a nonsymmetrical airfoil and also has relatively undesirable stall characteristics.

Advantage of a Symmetrical Airfoil:

- The fact that it can produce an equal amount of lift in either direction at the same positive or negative angle of attack.
- Negative lift can also be obtained with a cambered airfoil but at a very great negative angle. (this means you can fly a cambered airfoil inverted)
- The inverted angle must be great enough, though, that the effective lower area of the airfoils (which is now, in reality, the upper).

Cambered Airfoils:

Nonsymmetrical (cambered) airfoils may have a wide variety of upper and lower surface designs. The advantages of the nonsymmetrical airfoil are increased lift-drag ratios and more desirable stall characteristics. Non-symmetrical airfoils were not used in earlier helicopters because the center of pressure location moved too much when angle of attack was changed. Cambered airfoils (asymmetric) are the kind which can generate a lift at a zero angle of attack.

Definition of Airfoil:

A structure having a shape that provides lift, propulsion, stability, or directional control in a flying object. An airfoil-shaped body moved through a fluid produces an aerodynamic force.

Airfoil Nomenclature:

Figure 3: Airfoil Nomenclature

Description of NACA -9618:

Figure 4: Description of NACA -9618

Final Design:

Figure 5: Wing Model

Stress Analysis and Results:

First Iteration:

Wing with three spars

Table 1: Bending Moment for Three Spars in Iteration 1

Spars	Webs	I Section	20
		II Section	19
		III Section	18
		IV Section	17
		V Section	16
		VI Section	15
		VII Section	14
Ribs	I Rib	2.5	
	II Rib	2.3	
	III Rib	2.1	
	IV Rib	1.9	
	V Rib	1.7	
	VI Rib	1.5	
	VII Rib	1.3	
	VIII Rib	1.1	

Table 2: Thickness for Rib and Spar web in Iteration 1

Spars	Webs	I Section	20
		II Section	19
		III Section	18
		IV Section	17
		V Section	16
		VI Section	15
		VII Section	14
Ribs	I Rib	2.5	
	II Rib	2.3	
	III Rib	2.1	
	IV Rib	1.9	
	V Rib	1.7	
	VI Rib	1.5	
	VII Rib	1.3	
	VIII Rib	1.1	

Table 3: Area for Spar and Flange web in iteration 1

Sketch Section		Position From Wing Root	Area(Mm ²)
Spars	Flange	I Section	400
		II Section	380
		III Section	360
		IV Section	340
		V Section	320
		VI Section	300
		VII Section	280

Figure 6: Displacement analysis of the wing in iteration 1

Figure 7: Stress analysis of the wing in iteration 1
 Here displacement is 79.7mm and stress value is coming up to 1220N/mm². It's very high.
Final Iteration: (Iterations Were Made by Changing the Thickness of the Ribs):

Figure 8: Displacement analysis of the wing in iteration 4

Figure 9: Stress analysis of the wing in iteration 4

Table 4: Thickness for rib and spar web in iteration 4

Spars	Webs	I Section	48
		II Section	44
		III Section	40
		IV Section	36
		V Section	32
		VI Section	28
		VII Section	24
Ribs	I Rib	8	
	II Rib	7.5	
	III Rib	7	
	IV Rib	6.5	
	V Rib	6	
	VI Rib	5.5	
	VII Rib	5	
	VIII Rib	4.5	

Table 5: Area for Spar and Flange web in iteration 4

Sketch Section		Position From Wing Root	Area (Mm ²)
Spars	Flange	I Section	630
		II Section	600
		III Section	570
		IV Section	540
		V Section	510
		VI Section	480
		VII Section	420

Here displacement is 52 mm and stress value is coming up to 487 N/mm². Here the stress value is lying within the yield point of Aluminium.

Conclusion:

The Yield Stress value of Aluminium is 200 N/mm² to 600 N/mm². The Final result shows that the required stress value of 487 N/mm². Therefore our swept back wing can withstand the given loading condition. For a typical 150 seater regional aircraft we have analysed the swept back wing components by FEM, stresses are within the allowable limits. Introducing 3 spars with the designed thickness in our swept back increases the strength. Hence the design of our wing is safe and it is not easily buckle.

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